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EDITORIAL

The Board of Directors of the iiEP Institute decided to publish the abstracts of the posters presented in the Poster Shows promoted by the iiEP Institute and Universidad UNIDA. This decision adds one more item to the academic production of each student, Professor or interested party.

The event “Mostra Insternaciona de Pôsteres: Educação e Pesquisa” takes place in January and July, and the abstracts of the works presented are sent to the editorial board of this journal, for evaluation and release for publication, being done in December, in special edition of our magazine.

I congratulate the authors for the work presented at “Mostra” and also the editorial board of the journal that analyzed the abstracts for publication.

The CEO of the iiEP Institute and Editor of the Journal is satisfied with the release of another issue of the journal.

Ricardo De Bonis

CEO – Instituto iiEP

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MESO SPACE REPRESENTATION BY CHILDREN IN THE 1ST YEAR OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL: AN EXPERIENCE IN THE CLASSROOM

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ABSTRACT:

This report seeks to present observations and reflections that discuss a Geometry activity in a class of the 1st year of Elementary School in a school in the Municipal Network of São Paulo. For this, the studies by Rainiere and Colombo (2012) were used as a theoretical reference. The theme Spatial Relations is presented in the Common Curricular Base - BNCC (2017) in the unit called "Geometry", which defines for the 1st year the Object of Knowledge: "location of objects and people in space, using different reference points and vocabulary". The narrative presents an approach of reflection on the practice itself, based on the methodological and didactic propositions of the authors Rainiere and Colombo (2012). The activity was configured as an important path for learning spatial relationships and was identified in the students. an evolution in understanding the language needed to communicate the position or path of an object or person.

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NEUROSCIENCES IN EARLY CHILDHOOD

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT:

Neuroscience is the field of science that seeks to study and understand the nervous system, with the aim of explaining the mechanisms that occur in the brain and their relationship with behavior and learning. In the child she is an important part of human development. The research is of a bibliographical nature, where the collected data are interpreted having as a source of investigation the knowledge derived from books and publications as well as electronic scientific bases. The formation of brain processes occurs from birth where all stimuli and experiences provided and experienced during this stage will directly influence the development of their brain skills. Favoring not only their cognitive capacity, but all the individual's abilities. We concluded, according to a study carried out, that the evolutionary capacity of the brain becomes slower over the years, since brain plasticity decreases with age.

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HOMESCHOOLING UNDER DEBATE IN BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to analyze how the legal advance of Homeschooling in Brazil takes place. The hypothesis is that the discussion about Homeschooling is part of an ongoing political-ideological plan in the country. A bibliographic review was carried out based on specialized academic literature published in the last four years. Through a bibliographical review, it was concluded that the Homeschooling theme is complex and carries an ideological background that highlights an idea of educational dismantling in progress in the country.

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THE DIFFICULT GOODBYE OF THE GHOSTWRITER: REFLECTIONS ON THE PRACTICE AND UNDERSTANDING OF THE BRAZILIAN JUDICIARY

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the figure of the ghostwriter, also known in Brazil as “ghost writer”, is presented, as well as his work and the general peculiarities of his literary performance. As it turns out, far beyond a professional who has improved qualities in writing, this author, in most cases, is not even mentioned. He is behind the works, accompanying the development of the success that could have been his. In some cases, the “artistic ego” does not let him accept the forced separation, despite being aware of the clauses of the contract he signed with his client. The forced and distant view of unattainable success must not be easy, to some extent distressing, and it is not uncommon to end up in the Brazilian Courts. The practice of the ghostwriter is a long-standing reality in the production of literature, despite apparently being outside the scope of copyright protection.

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SCHOOL EDUCATION OF ADOLESCENTS DEPRIVED OF FREEDOM: BRAZILIAN REALITY AND LEGAL NOTION

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The right to education is defended within Brazilian legislation as a fundamental, social, public, subjective right and promoter of citizenship and human dignity. A right for all, education must be offered equally, observing the peculiarities of each case, as is the case of adolescents deprived of liberty who are serving socio-educational measures under the guardianship of the State. In this context, there is the legislative apparatus that guarantees their right and access to education, but the reality, in practice, is different. The present study aims to analyze the educational offer to adolescents deprived of their freedom, highlighting concepts related to the theme addressed, the legislative apparatus that currently deals with it and some data about it, in practice. For this, a qualitative research was used as a methodological procedure, in relation to the objective, it is an exploratory and descriptive research and on the research procedures, the study was characterized as bibliographic. The research was carried out in a virtual environment, in reliable databases such as Scielo, with scientific articles, monographs and thesis, with the descriptors: adolescents, Law, education, “socio-educational measure”, “private of liberty”. The resulting textual production is divided into two related titles, and the author’s impressions expressed in the final considerations as well as the conclusions.

Keywords: Teenagers. Right. Education. Private. Freedom. Socio-educational.

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CHALLENGES AND POSSIBILITIES IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS WITH DEAFNESS: EXPERIENCE REPORT DURING A PANDEMIC

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, we did not imagine that approaching others would be a health risk, and it was necessary to maintain social distance. This pandemic brought many challenges and new possibilities, as technologies were able to reach where our presence would not be possible. In view of this, a guiding question arises: how was it possible to help people with deafness during the pandemic in the educational process, where there were often communicative problems within the family? The theme chosen aims to present some activities aimed at the use of the Brazilian Sign Language (Libras), benefiting the deaf and their families. For the development of this work, an Innovative Pedagogy was thought (Freire, 1996) and in the words of Mahatma Gandhi: "Be the change you want to see in the world".

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POSSIBLE CHANGES IN THE ORAL HEALTH OF PEOPLE WITH DOWN SYNDROME: INTEGRATIVE LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Oral problems may involve not only physical health, but also economic aspects and social and psychological well-being. They can even affect self-esteem, demonstrating the importance of maintaining oral health in quality of life Method: integrative literature review based on the following guiding question: what are the possible changes in the oral health of people with Down Syndrome (DS). A consultation was carried out in the LILACS and MEDLINE databases, with the descriptors in Portuguese, “oral health” and “down syndrome” and in English adopted “oral health” and “down syndrome”. Articles published in the last five years (2016 to 2021) in Portuguese, English and Spanish and freely available in full were included in the study. Results: 7 articles were included that met the defined inclusion/exclusion criteria, 4 in LILACS and 3 in MEDLINE. Conclusion: it is necessary to carry out studies with better research designs and with adults and/or elderly people with DS, since most of the selected studies focused their research on children and/or adolescents with DS.

Keywords: Dentistry. Oral Health. Down’s syndrome.

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SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: THE CURRENT SITUATION OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT AND THE CONTRIBUTIONS OF PARTICIPATIVE MANAGEMENT TO SCHOOL SUCCESS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF DIAS D'AVILA – BAHIA

AUTHORS

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ABSTRACT

The study addresses the current situation of school management and how it has been managed in its dimensions, investigating whether the contributions of participatory management interfere with the learning of 3rd year students and other school segments in the municipality of Dias d'Ávila - Bahia. The quantitative/qualitative heterogeneous method used with a factual approach described in the period of six months of the second half of 2016. Data collection obtained through a semi-structured questionnaire, involving ten questions, analyzing the low IDEB indexes; high dropout rates and failure rates among students enrolled in Regular High School. In the analysis of the results, a set of managerial situations was identified which contributed to the facts that occurred. Conclusion from the point of view of the investigated actors detects a traditionalist management practice, impacting the results of the pedagogical praxis, its high rate of failures and abandonment. The research suggests the experiment of participatory management as an empirical method, the creation of a nucleus for monitoring graduates in educational units, seeking to strengthen the school institution and student learning. Keywords: Situation. School. Participative management. Students. Challenges. Teaching-Learning.

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HEPATIC STEATOSIS AND PREVALENCE OF NCDs IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING BARIATRIC SURGERY IN A REFERENCE SERVICE IN SÃO LUÍS-MA

AUTHORS

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- Adriana Kirley Santiago Monteiro
- Roberto Coelho Netto da Cunha Costa

ABSTRACT

Bariatric surgery and lifestyle changes are an effective method to facilitate weight loss, in addition to improving comorbidities in obese patients. This study aims to correlate hepatic steatosis with the prevalence of NCDs in patients undergoing bariatric surgery. Cross-sectional study with consultation of the database of patients monitored by the Bariatric Surgery Service of the University Hospital of UFMA, with descriptive and analytical characteristics. Fifty-two patients with hepatic steatosis were evaluated, 92.3% female, with a mean age of 42 ± 9.4 years and a mean BMI of $46 \pm 7.6 \text{ Kg/m}^2$. Systemic Arterial Hypertension was the most prevalent (55.8%), followed by Diabetes mellitus (51.9%). It is concluded that hepatic steatosis is a risk factor for CNCDs. The study was able to achieve its objectives by correlating the prevalence of hepatic steatosis and its association with CNCD in preoperative bariatric surgery patients. FRARE, L. et al, 2021; LEEMAN, M. et al., 2020.

KEYWORDS: hepatic steatosis. CNCD. bariatric.

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THE CLOUD IS THE DATA REVOLUTION

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT:

Show the technological advance, created by MICROSOFT, by Bill Gates, through his own creation, as well as his programs of: a) Operating System, b) Word (for use in texts), Excel (for use in spreadsheets), Power Point (for use in presentations) and Access (for use in Databases and research, based on past information), notably in the latter. From there begins a new System Similar to Access that uses Access (from Microsoft) in order to compile information from past data that comes with futuristic, technological, financial, probabilistic, mathematical ideas of scientific projections, with a view to a new world, called Metaverse, today understood as the Cloud (where all Access (Microsoft) information, prepared by Google, is stored, plus the use of John McCarthy's thesis.

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KNOWING THE END TO TRANSFORM THE BEGINNING

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT:

This poster seeks to create a pedagogical program aimed at students from public and private schools, where SEAP-RJ, through criminal police officers trained and qualified with Non-Violent Communication techniques, crime prevention, violence prevention due to intolerance of gender, race, color among others.

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SÃO JOAQUIM STATE SCHOOL AND HEALTH SURVEILLANCE IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF CONCEIÇÃO DO MATO DENTRO RAISING AWARENESS ABOUT DENGUE

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT:

The objective of this work was to give a lecture with an educational approach, carried out through a partnership between Municipal Health Surveillance and the São Joaquim State School for the prevention of dengue in the Municipality of Conceição do Mato Dentro. The lecture took place at the school during the month of March 2022 for about 300 elementary school students, where 40 students were evaluated and the data reported within this research. In the lecture, tools for mosquito identification, disease symptoms, prevention and measures to combat the vector were shared. An increase in knowledge was observed after interventions resulting from the School and Surveillance partnership, positive actions that will be repeated not only in epidemic periods, but also at other times.

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LEVEL OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF TEACHERS AT COLÉGIO ESTADUAL DA POLÍCIA MILITARY DE GOIÁS – CALDAS NOVAS - GO

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT

Through the development of Emotional Intelligence (EQ) in teachers, they favor the improvement in the teaching-learning process and in interpersonal relationships.

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MOURNING IN THE TIME OF COVID-19: STRATEGIES FOR FIGHTING PAIN AND PSYCHIC SUFFERING OF THE POPULATION

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 originated in China, with a high transmission capacity made a rapid emergence of the pandemic. With everyone very concerned about knowing the virus and all its procedures, mental health was the least notoriety, causing many to have deficiencies in this area. The present study aims to describe the strategies used by individuals to overcome grief, discuss the psychosocial impacts of mourning Covid-19, therefore, the focus is always on mental health in relation to the grief experienced. This is an integrative literature review study. The analysis of the articles allows us to infer that there is a lack of coping strategies for pain and psychic suffering of the population in the face of grief, since few manage to reach the service having to resort to alternative methods, also having a great perception that the number of professionals eligible for this action are extremely low. Through this study, we hope to help more health professionals pay attention to the mistakes previously made during the pandemic and encourage changes in the quality of care provided to the grieving population, not only during a pandemic, but at all times of mourning.

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THE BRAZILIAN PRISON SYSTEM FROM THE FOUCAULTIAN PERSPECTIVE

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT

The Brazilian Constitution guarantees, as one of the fundamental rights, that no one will be held that harms the dignity of the human person (art. 5, XLVIII), but the detention houses (penitentiaries) are overcrowded, unhealthy and without the minimum condition for resocialization.

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BUSINESS PLAN: OPENING OF THE BISTRÔ DO BIFF CASA DE CARNES BRANCH, AVENIDA SÃO JOÃO APARECIDA DE GOIÂNIA GO

AUTHOR

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this project is to make available to the consumer market a new meat shop offering products with quality standards, certified by the Sanitary Surveillance and Procon. An entrepreneurial strategy defined for differentiation and positioning in the market are the Barbecue Meat Kits with attractive prices, whose different personalized cuts meet the customer's needs.

THIRST

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